

Savings and Credit Cooperatives (Umurenge Sacco) and Rural Financial Inclusion in Kamonyi District: A Case Study of Musambira Sector

Jean Bosco Muvunyi

University of Lay Adventists of Kigali (UNILAK)

*Email: musco249@yahoo.fr

Abstract: The main objective of the study was to investigate the role of SACCOs to facilitate the rural community to use financial services, To assess the accessibility of SACCOs network by rural population in Kamonyi District, to study the level of financial services affordability by the rural population in Kamonyi District, To establish a relationship between SACCOs services and financial inclusion of rural population in Kamonyi District. The target population of the study constituted of all Customers of Umurenge SACCOs of Mbenezisonga within Musambira Sector in Kamonyi District. The research instruments used are questionnaires that were administered to 112 people including 7 employees of SACCOs of Mbenezisonga, 6 Leaders of cells of Musambira sector, 99 customers of SACCO Mbenezisonga whose 49 customers have the highest percentage of Savings and 50 have the lowest savings. Table 4.16 is giving the relationship between financial services of SACCO and rural financial inclusion whereby the respondents N is 112 and the significant level is 0.05 the results indicate that independent variable has positive low correlation to dependent variable equal to 0.204* and the p-value is 0.031 which is less than 0.05. When p-value is less than significant level, therefore researchers conclude that variables are correlated and null hypothesis is rejected and remains with alternative hypothesis. This means that there is a significant contribution of SACCOs to strengthen the rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District. We can therefore conclude SACCO Financial Services contribute positively to rural financial Inclusion. To improve and access financial services of SACCO within community's members, there is an urgent need on the part of encouraging the rural community members in using loans, the results from this study will help the decision makers to know the benefit and impact of Umurenge SACCO on financial inclusion in general and the impact of Umurenge Sacco on financial inclusion in particular.

I. Introduction to the Study

This study is focused on savings and credit cooperative organizations (Umurenge-SACCO) and rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District with Musambira Sector being the case study. This chapter presents the background to the study, the statement of the problem, research question, research objectives, hypothesis, significance of the study, justification (or rationale) of the study, theoretical/conceptual framework, scope and limitations and definition of terms and Operational definitions.

1.1. Background of the Study

Currently the world's poor people live and work in what is known as the informal economy. Even though they have little money, they still save, borrow and manage day-to-day expenses. However, without access to a bank, savings account, debit card, insurance, or line of credit, this affects relying on informal means of managing money and then financial inclusion come as a link to a country's economic and social development, and plays a role in reducing extreme poverty, it is considered as a state in which all people who can use them have access to a full range of quality, having financial services, provided at affordable prices, in a convenient manner, and with dignity for the clients. Financial services are delivered by a range of providers, most of them private, and reach everyone who can use them, including disabled, poor, and rural populations, (Zoodma-Sungur, 2014)

According to the Institute Asian Development Bank, the financial inclusion is now a global agenda for instance in Asia, and many countries are employing financial inclusion as an important part of their strategies to achieve inclusive growth. Regional discussions of the issue have also intensified; the Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) Finance Ministers' process has a dedicated forum looking at financial inclusion issues. The implementation of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Framework on Equitable Economic Development has been anchored on the promotion of financial literacy, among other initiatives. Development organizations have been responsive too (ADBI, 2014).

Financial inclusion is considered as the most recent item to be added explicitly to the social inclusion agenda and promotes the need for access among all segments of

society to a range of financial services at affordable cost. At the same time, the microfinance revolution, pioneered by the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh in the 1970s. This financial Institution was the first organization to be recognized for successfully implementing microfinance solutions, for which its founder, Mohammed Yunus, received the Nobel Peace Prize in 2006. The Grameen Bank focused on the reality that the formal financial system has not been successful in reaching the poor. Using peer monitoring and group-based approaches, microfinance agencies have shown that the poor are bankable and that innovative models can allow finance to benefit the poor. The narrow focus on credit has given way to a broader approach that includes micro-savings, micro-insurance, and remittance and payment transfers (ADBI, 2014).

Savings and Credit Co-operatives first appeared in Germany in the 1870's with Herman schultze- Delitsche, who established a saving and credit cooperative for minor artisans and the urban middle classes over the course of the industrial revolution, and FreidrichReifeisen, the founder of the rural saving and credit cooperatives, (Teta, 2016). The idea moved to North America in 1900 with European immigration. Canada, the United States, Australia and Ireland had the most established movements. In many regions of these countries SACCOs are much larger than the commercial banks. Globally there are almost 100 million individual members in 60 countries around the world and SACCOs are member of World Council of Credit Unions. Through this relationship SACCOs enjoys a reciprocal relationship with member countries throughout the world SACCOs was formed in 1993. It evolved from the Cape Credit Union League (SACCOs), which was formed in 1981 (RCA, 2018)

According Frank the Cooperative savings and credit societies in Rwanda have gained a wide recognition for the role of improving financial services to the low income households and thus contributing to economic development, this is an integral part of the country's financial system and should form an essential component of the financial system for increased savings mobilization, wider access to financial services and increased investments. In fact, Rwanda has a lot to share and a lot to study from fellow countries 'skills in financial inclusion and its effect on poverty mitigation. (Frank, 2015).

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The economic growth was a main concern of the government of Rwanda. Saving for the unexpected can be sound advice for anyone. Having money provides security and allows people to harness value for future prosperity. A bank account can increase savings, consumption and investment, satisfying basic needs and providing for innovation and job creation. However, financial services remain out of reach to 2 billion people around the world. The reasons for financial exclusion abound, including poverty, distrust of banks and an urban/rural divide approaches to bringing the excluded into the fold of finance have evolved over the years, from subsidizing bank branches in remote areas to enabling individuals and small to medium enterprises to execute transactions by mobile phone (Lee M. , 2017)

Currently, Rwanda's micro-finance sub-sector has 491 MFIs (including 478 SACCOs of which 416 are Umurenge SACCOs) where Umurenge SACCOs constitute 85% of all MFIs (Kevin, 2015). Based on the FINSCOPE report 2016 (FINSCOPE, 2016) shows that the formally served is about 68% of adults in Rwanda who are having and using formal financial products/services (Around four million individuals), including banked and other formal (non-bank) financial products/services and the Government of Rwanda's target of increasing the formal financial inclusion to 80% by 2017 has not yet been achieved. (MIGEPROF, 2016). Therefore the SACCOs financial services are not being accessed at the good level, the purpose of this study is therefore to find out the level of financial inclusion using SACCOs in Kamonyi District.

1.3. Research Questions

- a) How is SACCOs network accessible by rural population in Kamonyi District?
- b) What is the level of financial services affordability by the rural population in Kamonyi District?
- c) Is there any relationship between SACCOs services and financial inclusion of rural population in Kamonyi District?

1.4. Research Objectives

1.4.1. General Objective

The main objective of the study is to investigate the role of SACCOs to facilitate the rural community to use financial services.

1.4.2. Specific Objective

- a) To assess the accessibility of SACCOs network by rural population in Kamonyi District.
- b) To study the level of financial services affordability by the rural population in Kamonyi District.
- c) To establish a relationship between SACCOs services and financial inclusion of rural population in Kamonyi District.

1.5. Hypothesis

H_0 : There is a no contribution of SACCOs to strengthen the rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District

1.6. Significance of the Study

This study is very important to researchers, development planners and practitioners. It helps by providing a rich literature and useful information on improve the social economic development of Musambira Sector based on different strategies. As such, reference can always be made on it for future researches of the like. The research is not only important to the public but also to the private sector and civil organizations such as community based organizations. As for those who are involved in SACCO using it as a priority development tool, the research results gives them an opportunity to evaluate their activities and see whether they can use them for improvement of their field work. As a result, the work serves as a preliminary guideline to further development initiatives in Musambira Sector in particular and Republic of Rwanda in general.

As for academic purpose, the research brings about the necessary information to the development of the district. It also avails information to the development practitioners to serve them as contextual information. Finally, for researcher's personal purpose, this study serves an accomplishment to contributing to the district development and helps the

other fellow development scholars to get information on SACCO as well as rural financial inclusion and how it will spearhead the development in rural areas to the benefit of the people reside in rural area.

1.7. Justification of the Study

Financial inclusion is the one of strategy of poverty reduction, and this was motivated by seeing that the government Rwanda has put a high effort to support this financial inclusion based on the published reports of different institutions as well as following with Vision 2020 and EDPRS- II.

1.8. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

The independent variable in this study is SACCO as such it is a cooperative which operates in the financial system; it is a legal entity, in which individuals save their money and can get loans in order to invest in various activities, (MINECOFIN, 2018). The dependent variable is rural financial inclusion which means providing access to a full suite of quality financial services to everyone who can use it in rural community according to Institute for International (IIF) (Cheston, 2016).

The variables are summarized to the following figure.

Figure 4 1: Conceptual Framework (Researcher’s own figure)

1.9. Scope of the Study

This research was limited on the SACCO and rural financial inclusion in Musambira Sector. In terms of research period, this study covered the period between 2013 to 2018, the study will find out how SACCOs are impacting a financial inclusion to rural population in Kamonyi District.

1.10. Definition of Key Terms

Financial Inclusion: Account-holding is often used as the top-line indicator of financial inclusion, but genuine financial inclusion is a broader concept. It means providing access to a full suite of quality financial services to everyone who can use them, and making sure that people have the tools they need to manage their financial and economic lives. It goes beyond access to ensure usage and quality of products and services, and that customers can interact in the marketplace and throughout the supply chain (Cheston, 2016).

Informal Financial Institutions: Informal financial institutions defined as groups that are collectively owned and managed by members. These groups mobilize savings from individuals and provide short-term loans to members, and sometimes to non-members, at varying interest rates, depending on their structure. They operate at the community or village level in rural areas that often lack commercial or formal providers of financial products and services. Included in this group are: savings and credit cooperatives (SACCOs) rotating savings and credit associations (ROSCAs) accumulated savings and credit associations (ASCAs) village savings and loans associations (VSLAs) (TECHNOSERVE, 2014)

Microfinance: According to Term Strategy for Financial Inclusion in Fiji has defined the Microfinance as the provision of microloans (financial services) for the poor such as offering savings, transfers, insurance and credit, Microfinance products are tailored to the demographics, financial relationships and needs of the poor. Delivered by many types of institutions (commercial banks, state development banks, postal banks, MFI banks, NBFIs, coops and CUs, rural banks, NGOs, insurance coys, transfer payment coys, pawn shops, money lenders, informal groups & MNOs (Lami, 2009).

Financial Access Landscape: A measurement of usage of both formal and informal products across the four main product groups: transactions, savings, credit and insurance (STATISTICS, 2012)

Umurenge SACCOs: SACCOs initiated and formed with the support of the Government of Rwanda as a component of the National Savings Mobilization Strategy. One SACCO has been organized for each of the 416 sectors in Rwanda. Membership is based on individuals residing in the area of the SACCO. (STATISTICS, 2012).

1.11. Structure of the Study

This research is composed by five chapters made as follows: The chapter one gives background to the study, the statement of the problem, research question, research objectives, hypothesis, significance of the study, justification (or rationale) of the study, theoretical/conceptual framework, scope and limitations and definition of terms (Operational definitions). The second chapter is theoretical part of research, the literature review: it covers various elements of the as presented perspectives different writers, Empirical Review :It outlines reviews of the relationship between dependent & independent variables with published references, Research Gap demonstrating what research was not covered by previous researchers. The third chapter exactly deals with the methodology used while carrying out the research in order to get required information whereby sampling; questionnaires as well as interview. The fourth chapter presents the findings of the study and gives the representation and analysis of the result from those findings. The fifth chapter presents the conclusion, recommendation and suggestion.

II. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

The causality effect between MFIs including SACCO and rural financial inclusion has been main point to discuss for long years. Some researchers have found a positive effect of SACCOs to improve rural communities, others, in cross-country or geographical regions and income groups; have found a significance relationship for some geographical regions and none in others, especially for developing countries. Even though the role SACCOs and rural financial inclusion is accepted, the direction of causality is still a

debate. In this chapter, we present a review of literature on this issue from both theoretical and empirical grounds. There is acknowledgment that in countries at all income levels, there are still evidence showing that the rural financial inclusion not adequately serviced by the formal micro financial institutions.

2.2. Theoretical Review

A **SACCO** is a financial institution under the cooperative form. As such it is a cooperative which operates in the financial system; it is a legal entity, in which individuals save their money and can get loans in order to invest in various activities. The basic structure of the SACCOs and credit unions is what differentiates them from banks; they are user-owned financial intermediaries. Members typically have a “common bond” based on geographic area, employer, community, industry or other affiliation. Each member has equal voting rights regardless of their deposit amount or how many shares they own their principal products are savings and credit, however some offer money transfers, payment services and insurance. (Branch, 2005).

According to Rwanda cooperative agency website the Umurenge SACCOs offer basic Microfinance services with differences from a SACCO to another (it is often limited to the name of the loan targeting a different group of members with changes in the basic parameters like duration, interest, on deposit the SACCO has products current account where the time deposit is (4%), regarding retail loans SACCO offers Overdraft account, agriculture Livestock, Commerce, Construction, transportation (Motorbike/bicycle) Advance on salary, Handcraft, Health loan for group or individual (RCA, 2018).

According to Franka savings and credit cooperative is a cooperative financial organization owned and operated by and for its members, according to democratic principles, for the purpose of encouraging savings, using pooled funds to extend loans to members at reasonable rates of interest and providing retailed financial services to enable members improve their economic and social well-being. Saving and credit cooperatives are recognized by law and the cooperative society’s regulations. Some countries in Europe simply call them Credit Unions, others popular or people’s banks. The poor lack access to safe, formal deposit services institutions that mobilize deposit like banks, Micro

Finance Institutions and savings banks are often too far away, or the time and Procedures needed to complete transactions are too onerous (Frank, 2015).

According to Teta shows in her book that SACCO principles are the foundations of saving and credit cooperatives such as:

- Voluntary and open membership in a SACCO should be voluntary and open to all persons able to use their services and willing to accept the responsibilities of membership.
- Democratic Control, Administration and members' leadership SACCOs are democratic organizations controlled by their members, who actively participate in setting their policies and making decisions.
- Member Economic Participation The SACCO Societies should serve their members to improve their livelihood by giving safe place to save, teaching people how to generate income, how they can develop thrift culture, wise use of resources.

Continuous education, Training and Information to members. Education encourages member participation on their SACCO issues. This member's Participation is a key for the success to their SACCO development.

- Autonomous and self-help SACCO Societies are autonomous and self-help financial organizations controlled and managed by members.
- Cooperation among SACCO Societies SACCO Societies should cooperate among themselves in order to best serve of their members and the community.
- Concern for the community, SACCO societies should work for the sustainable development of their communities through the policies approved by their members. (Teta, 2016)

In Rwanda there is a regulatory framework for Supervising SACCOs, they are supervised under Microfinance Law No 40/2008 of August 26, 2008⁵ and the implementing Regulation No 02/2009,⁶ which govern the organization of microfinance activities. There is no specific regulation for SACCOs as a microfinance institution, but

there are specific provisions for SACCOs in the Microfinance Law and implementing regulation. The National Bank of Rwanda has a dedicated department for the supervision of microfinance institutions housed within the Financial Stability Directorate, parallel to the Department of Banking Supervision and the Department of Non-Bank Financial Institutions Supervision, which includes insurance and pension companies. For the period under review, the Microfinance Supervision Department has 77 inspectors, 60 of which are newly recruited by NBR and stationed in districts near SACCOs. This has revealed the cost of investing in financial inclusion as a public good. However, in the medium to long term, the NBR plans to devise a supervisory model that relies on a smaller number of inspectors (Francois, 2014).

Savings is the portion of income not spent on current expenditures, because a person does not know what will happen in the future, money should be saved to pay for unexpected events or emergencies, but some researchers like John Rouse in his book defined the savings as withholding something valuable for future use. To him there are two key elements of any saving activity which are: Discipline and sacrifice: where withholding something valuable for future use instead of consuming it immediately. Planning for the future: where saving is all about the future, about anticipating and preparing for possible risks and emergencies (a bad harvest, sickness or death), preparing for upcoming events and expenditures (payment of school fees, a marriage, old age, or funeral) or starting a new business or expanding an existing one (Rouse, 2002).

Transfer or receiving money for either paying of salaries, settlement of business transactions, paying of school fees, or for family support is common both for businesses and individuals. It needs an efficient, dependable and rational money transfer services whereby money can be deposited in one place and withdrawn in another in both town and countryside The money transfers market includes all types of customers, including individuals, businesses, and governments. For both international and domestic money transfers, clients from all levels of society use a variety of services, including formal, highly regulated channels and informal, unregulated ones Money transfers are used by people for many purposes: from everyday bill payment, to one-time-only money needs, to

delivering money from people in more-developed countries to families back home Among money transfer products, international remittances have received the most attention. The top three recipients of international remittances in 2006 were India US\$24,504 million, Mexico \$24,354 million, and China \$21,075 million (Isern, 2008).

2.3. Credit Cost

Credit is the trust which allows one party to provide money or resources to another party where that second party does not reimburse the first party immediately , but instead promises either to repay or return those resources (or other materials of equal value) at a later date According to Australian and Investment Securities Commission explain that once you are borrowing Money that you have to pay back later. If you use credit you end up paying more than if you paid in cash. This is because you have to pay back the money you borrowed plus interest, fees and charges (depending on how much you borrow). Also, if you don't pay the money back on time, there will be extra costs, it shows the type of credits such Credit cards, Home loans, Car loans Rent to buy deals, Rental of household items, Interest-free deals, Book up, Payday loans (short term and small amount loans) (ASIC, 2012).

Per example Credit cards, allow you to borrow up to a maximum spending limit. You can keep borrowing as long as you make regular minimum payments and stay below the limit. You usually pay an annual fee and are charged Interest on all transactions if you don't pay your full balance each month. If you use a card without, an interest-free period, you are charged interest from the date of your transaction. Unless you use a card that is interest-free and fee free, buying on credit will always cost you more than, if you pay for something upfront with cash (ASIC, 2017).

2.4. Deposit cost

According to Deshpande **The deposit** is a credit for the party (individual or organization) who placed it, and it may be taken back (withdrawn), transferred to some other party, or used for a purchase at a later date, in his research, Deshpande proved that a deposit has cost including both the financial (interest) cost and the various components of administrative cost. Interest on Deposits When money is deposited into a banking account, it earns interest. This means that, at fixed intervals, a small percentage

of the account's total is added to the amount of money already in the account. Interest can be compounded at different rates and frequencies depending on the bank or institution, so it is a good idea to look around for the best interest rates before committing to a savings account. A significant contributor to total deposit cost was financial cost, or the interest paid to depositors.(Deshpande, 2007).

Deshpande also outlined that there are four major types of administrative costs, or “core processes,” were identified as: Opening deposit accounts which includes activities like group formation, helping clients fill out paperwork to open accounts, recording client information and documentation, issuing passbook and check books; the second one is Servicing deposit accounts which includes customer-facing and back-office activities for existing account holders (e.g. taking deposits from clients in the field through roving collectors, replacing or issuing new passbooks, helping clients fill out deposit slips, clearing cheques, closing accounts),the third is handling cash transactions which refers to funds manipulation (e.g. recording cash in, deposits; and cash out, withdrawals), and back-office activities involving cash administration (e.g. supplying cash to branches, counting cash at the end of the day); the fourth is sustaining activities, which refers to all activities not directed exclusively to a particular service or product, but necessary for the operation of the institution (Deshpande, 2007).

2.5. Rural Financial Inclusion

The provision of financial services for rural farming and non-farming populations at all income levels, could probably be put into account that is why financial inclusion is considered as a major policy concern with governments across the world. The lack of access to a large percentage of working age adults to the formal financial sector is a genuine global policy concern. Financial inclusion has attracted and considered as a key element of the international initiatives to promote sustainable development. It can be instrumental to support economic welfare and reduce poverty.

Financial inclusion can be broadly defined as access by economic agents to formal financial services, e.g. the ability to make/receive payments, save/borrow and get insured. It is estimated that half of the world’s adult population has no account at a formal financial institution, and three quarters of poor people are unbanked. The situation can vary across

income groups, regions and countries however financial inclusion is a multiform concept. The CGAP2 states that “Financial inclusion efforts seek to ensure that all households and businesses, regardless of income level, have access to and can effectively use the appropriate financial services they need to improve their lives”. One will also focus on the quality of these services, which should be affordable, convenient, and provided with respect and dignity; others, including central banks, emphasize that financial services should be delivered in a competitive yet stable and properly regulated environment. (Bruno, 2015)

Financial inclusion intersects with a number of key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it adopted in September 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. These goals“ call for action by all countries, poor, rich and middle-income to promote prosperity while protecting the planet.” Among the SDGs closely connected to financial inclusion are objectives to: end poverty; achieve gender equality; “*promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth, employment, and decent work for all*” (a goal that is particularly germane to financial inclusion); and reduce inequality within and among countries. The FDIP team will monitor escort to reach the key targets associated with these SDGs as countries implement the 2030 Agenda (John, 2016).

According to the Asian Development Bank Institute(ADBI) the microfinance institutions (MFIs) often serve low-income clients and clients in underserved geographic areas, money transfers help MFIs meet their social goals by delivering an additional service demanded by low-income customers often at a cost lower than that of mainstream providers and value chain for the money transfer business includes : Primary activities devising Marketing and selling transfer products ,Originating and funding transfer orders, Sending transfer orders, Clearing transfer orders, Receiving transfer orders, Paying transfer orders, providing customer service, whereas support activities includes Finance, treasury and Internal control, Risk management, Technology, Human resources, Institution infrastructure (legal/regulatory, governance) (ADBI, 2014).

A key element of the financial inclusion strategy is creating an enabling environment for financial institutions and other competitors to provide a broader range of low-cost financial services to households. This includes savings and deposit products for

historically excluded clients, mobile money transfers (MMT), mobile and internet banking, agent banking, micro insurance and micro leasing. Much of the innovation has come from non-traditional players mobile phone operators, or new entrants to the Rwandan banking market rolling out agency banking models, which highlights the importance of an outward looking policy (Andrews, 2012)

2.6. Empirical Review

In terms of empirical studies, made supportive arguments as they found a positive and highly significant relationship of financial development through SACCOs on economic growth, the authors examine the relationship between financial development and economic growth using GDP as a proxy for economic growth and SACCOs as their case study. They find that an increase in cooperatives' credits and savings leads to a significant growth in GDP. More specifically, they observe that savings foster economic development more than credits, and thus conclude that SACCOs are not only important for GDP growth, but also policy makers should emphasize more on promoting savings amongst SACCOs members. (Teta, 2016).

Further, at the household level, Ksoll investigated the impact of savings and credit groups in Northern Malawi using a randomized control trial. Villages were randomly assigned to a control group or a treatment group. Residents of villages assigned to the treatment group were offered the Opportunity to join a savings and credit group, known as the Village Savings and Loan Association (VSLA) managed and funded by members, similarly to SACCOs. The authors analysed the impact of the VSLA membership two years later, and found a positive and significant effect on several outcomes such as the number of meals per day, households 'Expenditures, an increase in agricultural investments such as fertilizers, and an investment in Small-scale business, which led to a higher income for members. The authors however acknowledge the fact that the study has major limitations, the main one being external Validity, as results may be specific to cultural and economic conditions faced by the households considered in this study. Savings and credit groups have also been successful amongst women in rural areas.(Ksoll, 2016)

A study conducted in Cameroon by Jean-Marie Baland (Baland, 2007) from field observations of credit cooperatives in Cameroon, find out that a substantial number of members take loans that are fully collateralized by savings they held in the same institutions. 20% of the loans observed fall into this category. The price paid in terms of net interest payments is not negligible as it represents 13% of the amount borrowed. As traditional arguments such as credit rating or time inconsistent preferences cannot explain such behaviour in our specific setting on a different note, the effectiveness of SACCOs in the developing world has also been criticized in some studies. A research conducted in Cameroon, revealed a problem of excess borrowing and no incentive to save. Indeed, a substantial number of members use credit as a way to pretend that they are too poor to have available savings, this is mostly a strategy used to avoid requests for financial help from friends and family. One of the SACCOs members interviewed explained “When I borrow money, my wife thinks I don’t have money on my account. How can you have money and borrow? She thinks that I have no money and that is why I take a loan.

According to Clément Nsengimana in its research has find out that the VSLA have contributed positively towards transforming the lives of the rural poor as living conditions have improved; helps members start up small income generating projects; loans acquired from VSLA helps meet school fees; helps in meeting health related needs among others. Levels of community participation is moderately good as membership in VSLA is open; community members make and take decisions; community members get involved in VSLA activities; community members are involved in the implementation phase; community members are involved in monitoring and evaluation. (Nsengimana, 2012)

By Using data on identical and fraternal twins matched with data on their savings behaviour Henrik Cronqvist and Stephan Siegel (Siegel, 2010) find that an individual’s savings propensity is governed by both genetic predispositions, social transmission from parents to their children, and gene-environment interplay where certain environments moderate genetic influences. Genetic variation explains about 35 percent of the variation in savings rates across individuals, and this genetic effect is stronger in less constraining, high socioeconomic status environments. Parent-child transmission influences savings

for young individuals and those who grew up in a family environment with less competition for parental resources. Individual-specific life experiences are a very important explanation for behaviour in the savings domain, and strongest in urban communities.

The study conducted by Philip has shown that, although a positive relationship between financial literacy and financial inclusion exists, to a large extent the significance actually comes from the effect of financial literacy on households' awareness to the prevailing financial services. Thus, more financially literate households are more aware of the existence of the financial products and, empowered with awareness, such households have a significantly high probability of owning even some advanced financial products such as insurance and capital market products. (Philip, 2017).

According to the research conducted by Kaneza Ange, Jaya Shukla, Peter Mbabazi Mbabazize, Gaurav Bajpai in Rulindo District with main objective of examining the effects of microfinance on financial inclusion. The research instruments used are questionnaires to be administered to 64 employees and members of Umurenge SACCO. Literature was reviewed to enable the researcher to explicitly understand microfinance and financial inclusion; and to understand the theoretical links between microfinance and financial inclusion. The results from this study have shown further reveal that there is a significant relationship between the promotion of financial inclusion and community development. This has been evidenced by the respondent's confirmation of certain achievements in the community backed by the financial services as results of financial inclusion. (Kaneza Ange, 2012)

2.7. Research Gap

Although several previous studies have been conducted regarding microfinance (SACCOs) and financial inclusion, but this has rarely been covered by the researchers from the perspective of Rwandan context, meaning there is no empirical study that has shown the role of SACCO organizations (Umurenge SACCO) on rural financial inclusion therefore there is a gap in empirical study shows the percentages of correlation between SACCO and rural financial inclusion.

Based on the FINSCOPE report 2016 (FINSCOPE, 2016) shows that the formally served is about 68% of adults in Rwanda who are having and using formal financial products/services (Around four million individuals), including banked and other formal (non-bank) financial products/services and the Government of Rwanda's target of increasing the formal financial inclusion to 80% by 2017 has not yet been achieved. (MIGEPROF, 2016).

Therefore, the SACCOs financial services are not being accessed at the good level SACCO services have existed in Kamonyi District for a long time, therefore, the researcher would like to study how Umurenge Sacco's presence contributed in rural financial inclusion including financial awareness, Credit cost, Deposit cost and financial accessibility.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methods and processes that shall be followed by the researcher to conduct the study. This section outlines the Case Study Profile, Research Design, and Study Population, Sampling methods, Data Collection Instruments, Data analysis and Ethical Considerations.

3.1. Profile of the Case Study

This research was limited on the SACCO and rural financial inclusion in Musambira Sector as the one of sector of Kamonyi District. Geographically Kamonyi District was created by law no 29/2005 of 23 December 2005. It is one of the 8 districts in Southern Province, it has 655.5 Km², Its neighbouring Districts are Muhanga in West, Bugesera District and Nyarugenge districts in the East, Ruhango in South, Gakenke and Rurindo in the North. Its Functions are governed by law no 08/200608/2006 of 24 February 2006 determining the organisation and functioning of the district, Ministerial decree no 002/07.01 dated 23 June 2006 governing the functions of the district Council and Executive Committee and Ministerial decree no 004/07.01 dated 23 June 2006 establishing the functioning for the District Councils and Kigali City.

Kamonyi district comprises of 12 sectors which are Musambira, Rukoma, Ngamba, Runda, Rugalika, Karama, Gacurabwenge, Kayenzi, Kayumbu, Nyarubaka, Nyamiyaga and

Mugina, These sectors are subdivided into 59 Cells and 317 Villages. (DISTRCT, 2013). The district has now 12 Umurenge SACCOs named as the same as above sectors.

3.2. Research Design

The focus of the research was to obtain some qualitative and quantitative data that would facilitate a conclusion about savings and credit cooperative organizations (Umurenge SACCO) and rural financial inclusion in Rwanda with Musambira Sector as the case study. The data collection for descriptive research presents several advantages since it can provide a very multifaceted approach using interviews, observations and questionnaires. According to the Caleb Kim and Alicia Boyd have shown in his Book that a descriptive research design may be qualitative and quantitative as well and they defined the descriptive research as a type of research involves either identifying the characteristics of an observed phenomenon or exploring possible associations amount two or more phenomena (Boyd, 2017). It also involves collecting information through data review, survey, interviews, Or observation (Gay, 1987)

3.3. Study Population

Currently Umurenge Sacco Musambira has 7,800 Of customers, the research is limited to the customers of Umurenge SACCO that uses financial services, its staff as well as cell leaders, meaning that the research target population are SACCO's customers having high savings level and low savings from 2013, the staff or Umurenge SACCO of Musambira and cell leaders of Musambira Sector.

Table 3.1 detailed respondents from each group of target population

Category	Target population	Sample size	Sampling method
Umurenge Sacco Customers	7,800	99	Purposive sampling
Staff of SACCO Mbonezisonga/ Musambira	7	7	Census Survey

Leaders of Cells of Musambira Sector	6	6	Census Survey
Total	7813	112	

3.4. Sampling Methods

3.4.1. Purposive Sampling

Purposive sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources. This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest. In addition to knowledge and experience, the importance of availability and willingness to participate, and the ability to communicate experiences and opinions in an articulate, expressive, and reflective manner, (Lawrence A. Palinkas, 2018)

Purposive sampling techniques have also been referred to as non-probability sampling or purposive sampling. There are six types of purposive sampling procedures that are based on achieving representativeness or comparability: typical case sampling, extreme or deviant case sampling, intensity sampling, maximum variation sampling, homogeneous sampling, and reputational sampling. (Yu, 2007).

The researcher used a purposive sampling technique in order to focus on particular characteristics of population that are of interest, which are best enable to answer the research questions. Within Umurenge SACCO of Musambira 50customers that has a low savings level and 49 beneficiaries for high savings level have been selected by the study based on Slovin's formula.

3.4.1.1 Sample size determination using Slovin's formula

Slovin's formula is used to calculate an appropriate sample size from a population obviously, if you asked just one person in the population if they were vegetarian then their answer wouldn't be representative of everyone. While there are many formulas to calculate sample sizes, most of them require you to know something about the population, like the mean. But what if you knew nothing about your population? That's where Slovin's

formula comes in. When Slovin's formula is used If you have no idea about a population's behaviour, use Slovin's formula to find the sample size. The formula (sometimes written as Sloven's formula) was formulated by Slovin in 1960(Ryan, 2013).

The slovin's formula is calculated as follows: $n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$

n= Number of samples or sample size

N= Total population

e= Error tolerance

The population size of this research is 7813 people including 99 SACCOs customers,7 staff of SACCO and 6 cells leaders of Kamonyi Sector).We take a sampling error of 10%, and then the sample size was:

$$n = 7800/1+7800(0.1)^2$$

$$n = 7800/ 1+7800(0.1*0.1)$$

$$n = 7800/1+78$$

$$n=7800/79$$

$$n = 99+7+6$$

Therefore, the sample size was 112 respondents.

3.4.2. Census Survey

The entire group of objects or individuals about which information is wanted is called the population where the census is an attempt to gather information about every individual in a population according to the office for national statistics of United Kingdom, a census is a special type of survey where data is collected from all the units in the population of interest For example, if we were interested in the views of school children in the United Kingdom, and we surveyed all school children, we would be conducting a census The term census comes from the Latin word censere, meaning 'to assess, Every effort is made to include everyone, and that is why the Census is so important. It is the

only survey which provides a detailed picture of the entire population, and is unique because it covers everyone at the same time and asks the same core questions everywhere (ONS, 2001) after using Purposive Sampling a researcher also will use a Census survey technique in order to complete all information from all participants in the population that can be used to draw conclusions which will be best enable to answer the research questions. Within Umurenge SACCO of Musambira the entire 7 staff of SACCO and 6 cell leaders were carried out the study by using Census Survey and 99 customers of SACCO by using purposive Sampling, meaning that the whole sample of Beneficiaries, SACCO staff and 6 cell leaders is 112.

3.5. Data Collection Instruments

3.5.1. Questionnaire

Data were collected from selected participants through interviews administered by the research and a research assistant using a standardized questionnaire with both close ended and open ended questions which were given to respondents to give their views about the study topic

3.5.1. Secondary data

The researcher used annual reports as a secondary data in collection of the information. The researcher collected reports from the SACCOS stakeholders to have a more detailed insight about the functioning and execution of this Program. The secondary information sources include collection and analysis of data from reports, published material and information from National Bank of Rwanda. The reports were analysed and complement the primary data that were collected.

3.6. Data Analysis

The study used descriptive data analysis which combines both quantitative and qualitative data methods of analysis. Computer packages like statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel were used to generate charts, tables and figures. After collecting data, the researcher processed the collected data through editing, coding and tabulation as explained below. For the research to be quantitative and qualitative type, quantities were used to facilitate the action of data presentation and analysis to give a clear picture on the findings.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

In this research, a researcher has considered the sources of data which are both primary and secondary data. To collect such data, the research followed right protocols. A letter requesting permission to collect data from beneficiaries and Staff of SACCOs in Musambira Sector was provided by UNILAK. Before any contact with respondents gentle and polite presentation and introduction was made. Enough time to respond was given to the respondents and they have been assured about confidentiality.

IV. Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents empirical findings in reference to the research questions in chapter one. These findings were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. They were presented and analysed using frequency tables and percentages were used on research topic entitled savings and credit cooperative organisations (Umurenge SACCO) and rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District, a case study of Mbenezisonga SACCO/Musambira sector in Southern Province.

4.2. Profile of the Respondents

This section analyses the biodata of the respondents in order to determine the reliability of the data provided by the respondents.

4.2.1. Gender

Table 4.1. Shows gender of the respondents

	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	20	17.9	17.9	17.9
	Female	92	82.1	82.1	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2018

From table 4.1. Shows that 82.1% were female while 17.9% males. This shows that Data obtained is free of gender bias since both male and female were represented.

4.2.2. Occupation level of the Respondents

Table 4.3. Shows Occupation of the respondents

Occupation		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Farmer	94	83.9	83.9	83.9
	Trader	7	6.3	6.3	90.2
	Craft	10	8.9	8.9	99.1
	State Employee	1	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

From table 4.3. Show that 0.9 % were state employee 8.9% were craft 6.3% were Traders, while 83.9 % were famers.

4.2.3. Educational level of the respondents

Table 4.4. Educational level of the respondents					
	Education	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Primary	84	75.0	75.0	75.0
	Vocational training	20	17.9	17.9	92.9
	Secondary	8	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

From table 4.4 Shows that 7.1% of the respondents were diploma holders, 17.9% finished Technical vocational education training (TVET) and finally 75% had primary school level. This implies that the respondents are educated meaning they could read, understand and interpret questionnaires reliably. The data collected is believed to be reliable and was thus processed to present findings.

4.2.4. Experience of Beneficiaries to use financial services of Umurenge

	Experience of working with Umurenge SACCO	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Two Years	15	13.4	13.4	13.4
	Three Years	29	25.9	25.9	39.3
	More Than Three Years	68	60.7	60.7	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

From table 4.5. shows that 60.7% of the respondents said that they work with Umurenge SACCO more than three Years,25.9% said that they worked with Umurenge SACCO three years ago,13.4% are working with Umurenge SACCO Two Years Ago

4.3. Accessibility of SACCO Network

	Distance from home to the SACCO does not require me a long time	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	26	23.2	23.2	23.2

	Strongly Agree	86	76.8	76.8	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2016

From table 4.6 shows that 76.8.% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed that the time that is used to reach at Umurenge SACCO is not problem and 23.2% of the respondents said that they are agreed This implies that the data provided reflected the views of the entire population and the respondents' perceptions are reaching at SACCO without a matter of time and they gave matured view for the purpose of this research.

4.4. Financial Awareness

Table 4.7. Customers Participation on financial services training at Umurenge SACCOs					
financial services training participation		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	105	93.8	93.8	93.8
	Disagree	2	1.8	1.8	95.5
	Agree	1	.9	.9	96.4
	Strongly Agree	4	3.6	3.6	100.0
Total		112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

From table 4.7. Shows that 3.6 % of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed and 0.9 % of the respondents said that they are agreed, 1.8 % are disagreed whereas 93.8% are Strongly Disagree meaning that the majority of population shows that there is a need of training to aware of financial services offered by Umurenge SACCO.

4.4.1. Awareness on deposit and loan information

Table 4.8. perception of the respondents to be informed on deposit and loan					
I can have information related to deposit/loan as well as my bank account		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	80	71.4	71.4	79.5
	Agree	10	8.9	8.9	88.4
	Strongly Agree	13	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

From table 4.8. Shows that 11.6 % of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed and 8.9 % of the respondents said that they are agreed, 71.4 % are disagreed whereas 8.0% are Strongly Disagreed meaning that the majority of population shows that there are not informed about their amount deposited as well as being aware on loans offered by Umurenge SACCO.

4.4.2. Credit cost

Table 4.9. Shows the perception of the respondents on Credit cost					
I am happy for an interest rate that is charged to request loan/credit		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	112	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2018

From table 4.9. Shows that 100% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed, meaning that the interest rate on loan is normal.

4.4.3. Deposit cost

Table 4.10. Perception of the respondents on deposit cost					
fee of charges requested is affordable on the clients of Umurenge SACCO		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	112	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.10. Shows that 100 % of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed on the fees charged is affordable.

4.5. Financial services Affordability

Table 4.11. Perception of the respondents on Savings					
I like Savings at Umurenge SACCO than other financial services		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	40	35.7	35.7	35.7
	Strongly Agree	72	64.3	64.3	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.11. Shows that 64.3% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed, 35.7 % were agreed, this implies that the respondents are very happy to save within Umurenge SACCO.

4.5.1. Credit

Table 4.12. Perception of the respondents on Credit					
I like requesting loan at Umurenge SACOO than other financial services		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	59	52.7	52.7	52.7
	Disagree	36	32.1	32.1	84.8
	Strongly Agree	17	15.2	15.2	100.0
Total		112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.12. Shows that 15.2% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed, 32.1 % were disagreed, while 52.7 are strongly disagreed

4.5.2. Money transfer

Table 4.13. Perception of the respondents on Money transfer					
I used money transfer at Umurenge SACCO than other financial services		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	112	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.13. Shows that 100% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed, the responded that there are not using money transfer within Umurenge SACCO.

4.5.3. Payment service within Umurenge SACCO

Table 4.14. Perception of the respondents on Payment services					
I used to make payment within Umurenge SACCO		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

than other financial services					
Valid	Agree	88	78.6	78.6	78.6
	Strongly Agree	24	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	112	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.14. Shows that 21.4% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed while 78.6 were agreed, this indicates the majority of customers are using the payment services within Umurenge SACCO.

4.5.3.1. Change after joining Umurenge SACCO

Table 4.15. Change after joining the SACCOs Services					
My standard life has charged After joining the SACCOs Services		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	112	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.15. Shows that 100% of the respondents showed they are strongly agreed. This indicates the majority of customers are changing their life within Umurenge SACCO

4.6. Relationship between financial services of SACCO and rural financial inclusion

Table 4.16. Relationship between financial services of SACCO and rural Financial inclusion			
Relationship		Financial services of Umurenge SACCOs	Rural Financial inclusion

Financial services of Umurenge SACCOs	Pearson Correlation	1	.204*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.031
	N	112	112
Rural Financial inclusion	Pearson Correlation	.204*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.031	
	N	112	112
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Primary data, 2018

Table 4.16. is giving the relationship between financial services of SACCO and rural financial inclusion whereby the respondents N is 112 and the significant level is 0.05 the results indicate that independent variable has positive low correlation to dependent variable equal to 0.204* and the p-value is 0.031 which is less than 0.05. When p-value is less than significant level, therefore researchers conclude that variables are correlated and **null hypothesis is rejected and remains with alternative hypothesis**. This means that there is a significant contribution of SACCOs to strengthen the rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District. We can therefore conclude SACCO Financial Services contribute positively to rural financial Inclusion.

V. FINDINGS, CONCLUSION ANDRECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction

The chapter covers the summary, conclusion and recommendation of the findings. The summary covers the findings in relation to the objective of the study. The summary is followed by the conclusion which is based on the findings of the study and recommendations to the challenges facing the Umurenge SACCO.

5.2. Summary of Findings

The study was mainly concerned about savings and credit cooperative organizations (Umurenge-SACCO) and rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District with

Imbereheza SACCO/Musambira Sector being the case study. This summary was based on the objectives of the study.

5.2.1. Accessibility of SACCOs Network

Based on The Table 4.6 the findings on savings and credit cooperative organizations (Umurenge-SACCO) and rural financial inclusion shows the highest percentage of respondents is 76.8% who said to reach at Umurenge SACCO does not require a long time therefore we can conclude that an accessibility of Umurenge SACCOs network is not affecting the financial services of SACCO

5.2.2. Financial Service Affordability

Reference on table 4.11, table 4.12 and table 4.13 show that the financial service are being accessible on good way, The finding shows that the 64.3% of respondents further stated that the they are using financial services including Savings, loans, payments except money transfer which is not being used due to ongoing computerized infrastructures, therefore we can conclude that We can therefore conclude that Financial services are accessible and affordable on rural financial inclusion.

5.2.3. Relationship between SACCOs and Financial Inclusion in Kamonyi

As is indicated on the table 16.16 gave the relationship between Financial services of Umurenge SACCO and rural financial inclusion whereby the respondents N is 112 and the significant level is 0.05, The findings stated that SACCOs is contributing in strengthen the rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi, The results showed a very strong significant positive relationship between SACCO and rural financial inclusion Level, the results indicate that independent variable has positive high correlation to dependent variable. A Pearson's correlation reporting using the small letter r. So, in this case we might say something like: SACCO and rural financial inclusion Level ($r=.204^*$, $p<0.05$). The p-value is .031 which is less than 0.05 when p-value is less than significant level, hence researchers conclude that variables are correlated and null hypothesis is rejected and remains with alternative hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship between contributions of savings and credit cooperative to strengthen the rural financial inclusion. It is therefore concluded that **financial services of Umurenge SACCO positively contribute to the rural financial inclusion.**

5.3. Conclusion

Based on the findings it was established that The financial services of Umurenge SACCO plays a significant role in strengthen rural financial inclusion This was implied by present findings from research, the table 4.5 gave the relationship between The financial services of Umurenge SACCO and rural Financial inclusion whereby the respondents N is 112 and the significant level is 0.05 the results indicate that independent variable has positive high correlation to dependent variable equal to 0.204* and the p-value is 0.031 which is less than 0.05. When p-value is less than significant level, therefore researchers conclude that variables are correlated and null hypothesis is rejected and remains with alternative hypothesis. This means that there is a significant contribution of SACCOs to strengthen the rural financial inclusion in Kamonyi District. We can therefore conclude SACCO Financial Services contribute to positive to rural financial Inclusion.

5.4. Recommendations

The researcher came up with the following recommendations. The management of Umurenge SACCO should increase the number of trainees in using financial services, the training could be targeting the general committee of SACCO this will increase the financial awareness of SACCO customers. The management of SACCO could increase sensitization of Umurenge SACCO's services this will encourage the number of customers using its services in order to meet the organization's goal. The management of SACCO could set a mechanism of sensitize its customers to request a loan because the number of beneficiaries requesting loan is still low. The SACCO with collaboration of RCA should buy a software that could be used in money transfer (debit and credit card) and any other financial services, this will further promote the performance of SACCO.

5.5. Scope for further studies

Given the limited scope of this study, the results cannot be generalized to all savings and credit cooperative organizations and rural financial inclusion in the Republic of Rwanda and elsewhere. Therefore, there is a need to undertake similar studies in other contexts to be able to obtain a wider picture of the situation at hand of small community organized projects to meant to support financial inclusion at such lower levels. Therefore, the following are suggested areas for further research:

- Financial Inclusion and people with disability entrepreneurship
- SACCOs and women financial access
- SACCOs and youth Entrepreneurship in Rural area of Rwanda

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I thank the Almighty God my creator who has at all times been with me throughout my life.

I am sincerely grateful to Dr. MBERA Zenon who accepted to supervise this thesis.

I am also thankful to every one of my lecturers who inculcated in me project management knowledge.

I also extend my gratitude to all those who have contributed to my formal education. These include those who taught me in primary, secondary and higher education.

It would not be polite to leave my family unmentioned for the contributed to my growth including my cousin JYAMBERE Laurien who used to encourage me to be specialised in project management. My wife UMUFITE Odine for her love and advice. Lastly, my thanks go to my fellow students in business administration /project management.

References

- [1] ADBI. (2014). Tokyo: Institute Asian Development Bank
- [2] ADBI. (2014). Financial Inclusion in Asia Country Surveys. Tokyo
- [3] Andrews, M. (2012). Financial Sector Development Program II
- [4] Ange, K. (2014). Financial inclusion, Microfinance, Saving and Credit Cooperative. International Journal of Advanced Research , 738
- [5] ATM. (2017). Access to Cash: The First Step toward Financial Inclusion
- [6] Authority, F. C. (2017). Payment Services and Electronic Money –Our Approach. The North Colonnade Canary
- [7] Baland, J.-M. (2007). Pretending to be poor: borrowing to escape forced solidarity in credit cooperatives in Cameroon

- [8] Bigirimana, M. (January, 2018). Financial Inclusion in Rwanda: an Analysis of Role Played by Commercial Banks
- [9] Branch, B. (2005). CGAP. Washington, DC
- [10] Bruno, T. (2015). Statistical challenges related to financial inclusion
- [11] Boyd, C. K. (2017). Research Method and Practice
- [12] CGAP. (December 2007). the true cost of deposit mobilization
- [13] Cheston, S. (2016). Insights From Banks In Emerging Markets
- [14] Cheston, S. (2016). The Business Of Financial Inclusion Insights From Banks In Emerging Markets. Piyush Gupta
- [15] Clarisse, I. R. (2014). The Impact Of Financial Inclusion On
- [16] Deshpande, R. (2007). the true cost of deposit mobilization.
- [17] DISTRCT, K. (2013). Kamonyi District Audir Report
- [18] Finance, I. o. (2016). the business of financial inclusion:insights from banks in emerging markets
- [19] Finscope. (2016). Financial Inclusion In Rwanda 2016. Kigali Rwanda: Access To Finance Rwanda (Afr)
- [20] Francois, K. (2014). Rwanda's financial inclusion success story umurenge Sacco
- [21] Frank, T. (2015). European Centre for Research Training and Development UK, 2.
- [22] Frank, T. (2015). Savings And Credit Cooperatives Services' Terms and Members' Economic Development in Rwanda: European Centre for Research Training and Development, 7.
- [23] Frank, T. (2013). Savings And Credit Cooperatives (Sacco's) Services' Terms and Members' Economic. European Centre for Research Training and Development UK
- [24] IFC. (2011). Telling our story
- [25] Inclusion, A. f. (2014). Rwanda's Financial Inclusion Success Story. National Bank Of Rwanda
- [26] Inclusion, A. f. (2014). Rwanda's Financial Inclusion Success Story Umurenge SACCOs

- [27] INDIA, C. O. (2011). Proviassial popolation totals. Census of India
- [28] Institute, A. D. (2014)
- [29] Isern, J. (2008). Making Money Transfers
- [30] John. (2016). Advancing equitable Financial Ecosystems.Washington, Dc
- [31] Kaneza Ange, J. S. (2012). Microfinance Services as a Key Driver of Financial Inclusion in Rwanda
- [32] Kevin, K. S. (2015). Rwanda's Financial Inclusion Rwanda Success Story: Umurenge Sacco
- [33] Ksoll. (2016). Impact of Village Savings and Loan Associations Evidence from a cluster randomized trial.
- [34] Lami. (2009). Definition & evolution of microfinance . Fiji.
- [35] Lee, M. (2017). Access to Cash:The First Step toward Financial Inclusion.Atmia
- [36] MIGEPROF. (2016). final report of the strategy on women and youth access to finance (2016-2020). Kigali: MIGEPROF.
- [37] MINECOFIN). (2009). Umurenge Saccos Strategy
- [38] Mwangi, P. G. (February 2013). International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology. Credit Risk Management Practices by Oil Companies in Kenya ,74
- [39] Nsengimana, C. (2012). the contribution of Village Savings and Loan Association to the reduction of poverty among the rural community members in Rulindo District.
- [40] ONS. (2001). Office for national statistics. Newport.
- [41] Philip, A. B. (2017). Financial Literacy, Awareness and Inclusion.
- [42] Quora. (2018, May 30). In-banking-does-credit-cost-and-cost-of-funds-mean-the-same.
- [43] Rouse, J. (2002). The group savings resource book ce book.
- [44] Rutherford, S. (1999). Savings And The Poor.
- [45] Rwanda, N. B. (2015). Rwanda's Financial Inclusion Rwanda's Financial Inclusion. Brazzaville, Congo: Kavugizo Shyamba

- [46] RWANDA, N. I. (2012). Gender Monitoring Office Access To Finance . Gender Statistics Publication.
- [47] Ryan, T. (2013). Sample Size Determination and Power. John Wiley and Sons.
- [48] Siegel, C. a. (2010). The Origins of Savings Behavior.
- [49] STATISTICS, N. I. (2012). Access to Finance.
- [50] TECHNOSERVE. (2014). Business solutions to poverty.
- [51] Teta, S. R. (2016). Savings Groups and Banks: Complements .
- [52] Tumwine Frank, D. M. (2015). International Journal of Community and Cooperative Studies. Savings And Credit Cooperatives (Sacco's) Services' Terms and Members' Economic , 2-3.
- [53] Tumwine Frank, D. M. (June 2015). International Journal of Community and Cooperative Studies. International Journal of Community and Cooperative Studies .
- [54] UNDP. (2014). Rwanda 2014 National Human Development Report.
- [55] UNDP. (2014). Rwanda National Human Development Report 2014.
- [56] Uronu, A. (2018). Prospects and Challenges of Collective Action in Extending Financial Services among Rural Smallholders Farmers in Tanzania. Moshi.
- [57] Yu, C. T. (2007). Journal of Mixed Methods Research . Journal of Mixed Methods Research, 80
- [58] Zoodsma-Sungur, A. (2014). The importance of financial inclusion.
- [59] Akrani, G. (2018, June 2). What is Finance? Meaning Definition Features of Finance. Retrieved from alyan-city.blogspot: <http://kalyan-city.blogspot.com/2011/11/what-is-finance-meaning-definition.html>
- [60] businessdictionary. (2018, June 3). small-business. Retrieved from businessdictionary: <http://www.businessdictionary.com/topic/small-business/>
- [61] CGAP. (2018, May 5). Advancing financial inclusion to improve the lives of the poor. Retrieved from CGAP: <http://www.cgap.org/about/faq/what-financial-inclusion-and-why-it-important>

- [62] Dallas, F. R. (2018, May 30). Not All Loans Are the Same. Retrieved from jumpstart: www.jumpstart.org
- [63] ec.europa.eu. (2018, June 3). financial awareness . Retrieved from ec.europa.eu: <https://ec.europa.eu/epale/en/blog/5-findings-about-link-between-financial-awareness-and-financial-stability>
- [64] investopedia. (2018, June 3). Deposit. Retrieved from investopedia: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/deposit.asp>
- [65] Investor, O. o. (2018, June 2). Saving and Investing. Retrieved from Investor: www.Investor.gov
- [66] Lawrence A. Palinkas, P. (2018, July 8). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. Retrieved from ncb: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4012002/#R36>
- [67] Investopedia. (2018, May 8). Automated Teller Machine - ATM. Retrieved from nvestopedia: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/a/atm.asp>
- [68] Lee, S. (2018, June 2). Introduction to Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) Part I. Retrieved from calvertimpactcapita: <https://www.calvertimpactcapital.org/blog/683-intro-to-mfis>
- [69] MINECOFIN. (2018, May 6). Umurenge SACOS startegy. Retrieved from Umurenge SacosStrategy: <http://www.rca.gov.rw>
- [70] Retrieved from quora: <https://www.quora.com/In-banking-does-credit-cost-and-cost-of-funds-mean-the-same>
- [71] RCA. (2018, May 5). Retrieved from <http://www.rca.gov.rw/about-sacco/background/#.Wu9zxaSFPIV>
- [72] RCA. (2018, May 2). Retrieved from <http://www.rca.gov.rw/about-sacco/products-services/#.WxLHDu6FPIV>
- [73] ReserachGate. (2018, May 8). What are the variables that one should consider for measuring financial inclusion? Retrieved from ReserachGate: https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_are_the_variables_that_may_consider_for_measuring_financial_inclusion

- [74] Smetimes. (2018, June 3). New Msme Definition. Retrieved From Smetimes: <http://www.smetimes.in/smetimes/editorial/2018/Feb/13/new-msme-definition36451.html>
- [75] wells-fargo-works. (2018, June 3). The cost of credit: Key terms to consider. Retrieved from wells-fargo-works: <https://wellsfargoworks.com/business-credit-center/article/the-cost-of-credit-key-terms-to-consider>
- [76] wizzcash. (2018, June 2). Small Loans. Retrieved from wizzcash: <https://www.wizzcash.com/small-loans/>